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Deliverable overview

Deliverable title: Report on transformative change potential and piloting in Strengthening management of R&I human capital

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Deliverable summary: D 2.3 consists of an introduction to WP 2's work on strengthening management of R&I human capital, followed by its four focal areas:

- Attracting and Retaining Talents at All Career Stages
- Performance and Development Review
- Gender-Related Equality Standards
- Work-life balance approaches

In the concluding section, future perspectives on strengthening management of R&I human capital are outlined, including obstacles, challenges and what has been learnt so far.

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1. Strengthening management of R&I human capital

In the dynamic landscape of academic collaborations, European University Alliances stand at the forefront of pioneering human resource (HR) strategies aimed at enhancing the academic environment. This comprehensive overview delves into the multifaceted efforts of our Alliance in attracting and retaining talent across all career stages, developing robust performance and development review systems, advancing gender-related equality standards, and promoting effective work-life balance approaches. It encapsulates the collaborative endeavours of our institutions, highlighting initiatives in exchanging best practices, supporting diverse academic communities, including those affected by crises like the Ukraine conflict.

These initiatives, while ambitious and forward-thinking, are not without their challenges and obstacles. From integrating diverse systems and practices to addressing the nuances of gender equality and work-life balance in different cultural and legal contexts, this final report from WP 2 Strengthening R&I human capital explores the complexities and learnings of implementing effective HR policies within these extensive academic networks.

2. Attracting and Retaining Talents at All Career Stages

Promotion programs are vital for career advancement and recognition in academia. By exchanging and adopting best practices, universities can create more appealing and equitable promotion paths for their faculty and staff. This not only helps in retaining current talents but also in attracting new ones by showcasing a clear and rewarding career trajectory.

Training schemes

Training schemes are essential for continuous professional development to ensure that university members are up to date with the latest knowledge and skills in their fields. By sharing and implementing effective training programs, universities can foster an environment of learning and growth, which is attractive to academics at all stages of their careers. In the future, we will consider sharing the pool of trainings for at least some of the programs. But it was also mentioned that there was a highlighted difficulty in terms of legislation and taxation, which needs to be resolved before sharing the pool of training can take place.

Welcoming and Recruiting Strategies

The strategies for welcoming and recruiting new university members are key to creating a supportive and inclusive university culture. This includes support for Selection Committees, orientation programs, mentorship systems, and integration activities that help new members adjust and feel valued in their new environment. By exchanging best practices in these areas, universities can enhance their attractiveness as employers and support systems for new talents.

Support for Crisis Situations

The response to the Ukraine crisis by providing support to Ukrainian researchers and students is a prime example of the adaptive and empathetic approach of these alliances. Offering financial aid, language courses, and psychological support in times of crisis not only aids those directly affected

but also reinforces the alliance's commitment to its community's well-being. This kind of support system is crucial in retaining talents who might otherwise be forced to leave due to external circumstances. Taking in account the geographical placement, UW provided massive help which was shared with the partners:

- Educational support - a nationwide platform for online recruitment of candidates from Ukraine (ukraina.irk.edu.pl) - the aim is to make it easier for Ukrainian citizens who are students, doctoral students or employees of Ukrainian universities and research institutes to find their way around the educational and job offers they can avail of in Poland.
- Social support - In March 2022, amendments to the University of Warsaw's Student Benefit Regulations came into force, which significantly simplified access to a maintenance grant and an allowance for those affected by warfare and complied with the provisions of the Act of 12 March 2022 on Assistance to Ukrainian Citizens in Connection with Armed Conflict on the Territory of that State.
- Support for the universities - The assistance offered by the University of Warsaw was also aimed at Ukrainian universities. Their needs were verified during numerous meetings between representatives of the UW authorities and the Ukrainian partners.
- Health support - With the joint efforts of the faculty's research staff and final-year students of optometry and European studies in spectacle optics and optometry, an eye examination was provided for refugees from Ukraine, which, if necessary, was complemented by new glasses obtained through cooperation with companies such as HOYA and OPTIBLOK. Those from Ukraine who needed an internal medicine consultation could count on the support of Dr Józef Haczynski, an internal medicine doctor and member of UW Faculty of Management. Medical first-aid kits purchased by the University complemented the offer in this regard.
- Employment support- The University's doors were open to everyone, not only to university applicants, but also to people who wanted to start building their new lives by working at the University of Warsaw. It was possible to employ people from Ukraine in faculties, academic units and research groups.
- Other actions - A special tab in Polish and English is maintained on the homepage, where information is collected on support opportunities offered by the UW. It publishes the most important information on social, legal and psychological support, translations, educational activities, collections and other initiatives undertaken at the university. In order to better coordinate the many activities undertaken at the university and to promote information about them, a special e-mail address has also been set up for sending information on initiatives for people from Ukraine.

Exchange of Best Practices

The exchange of best practices among WP2 members and experts from participating universities is a cornerstone of this initiative, e.g., UW study visit at UCPH and online meeting between UW and UHD. It allows for the pooling of diverse experiences and expertise, leading to more robust and well-rounded HR policies. This collaborative approach ensures that the strategies developed are informed by a wide range of perspectives and are more likely to be effective in different institutional contexts.

Overall, this represented a comprehensive approach to managing human resources in academia. It addresses the entire spectrum of an academic career, from recruitment and welcome to ongoing

development and support in crisis situations. By focusing on these areas, European University Alliances aim to create a more dynamic, supportive, and attractive academic environment that can thrive in the face of both routine challenges and unexpected crises.

3. Performance and Development Review

The University of Copenhagen's (UCPH) Performance and Development Review scheme, currently being piloted after adjustments at the University of Warsaw (UW), represents a significant initiative in advancing career development for academic staff, particularly early career stage researchers. This program highlights several key aspects:

Focus on Career Development

The career development scheme is designed to cater specifically to the needs of early and mid-level researchers, a critical stage where targeted support can significantly impact career trajectories. By focusing on this group, the initiative directly addresses the career development needs at stages where guidance is most impactful.

Personalized Guidance

A cornerstone of the scheme is the emphasis on personalized guidance. This approach recognizes that career paths in academia can be highly individualized, and that personal guidance can better address the specific aspirations, strengths, and development needs of each researcher and manager. Personalized plans and feedback are more likely to result in effective career development compared to one-size-fits-all approaches.

Continuous Career Progression

The initiative stresses the importance of continuous progression in an academic career. This aspect acknowledges that career development is not a static or one-time event but a continuous process requiring regular assessment, feedback, and adaptation of goals and strategies.

Implementation at UW and CU

The piloting of this scheme at UW (the scheme at UCPH was an inspiration for the mentoring programme at UW, however the scheme was not implemented in 1:1 ratio and its consideration for implementation at CU (Charles University) indicates a broader recognition of its potential benefits across different university contexts. The adoption and adaptation of this scheme by other universities in the alliance demonstrates a commitment to leveraging best practices for mutual benefit.

Role of Managers/Senior academics

The inclusion of managers/senior academics in this scheme is particularly noteworthy. In academia, the role of a manager or a senior academic in guiding and shaping the careers of their juniors is crucial. This scheme likely involves training for managers/senior academics on how to effectively mentor and develop their teams, which can have a profound impact on the overall academic environment and output.

Cross-Institutional Learning

The exchange of this practice between UCPH, UW, and potentially CU reflects the value of cross-institutional learning within European University Alliances. By sharing and adapting successful programs, these institutions can and will enhance their own HR practices and contribute to a more cohesive and effective academic community.

In summary, UCPH's Performance and Development Review scheme represents a thoughtful approach to fostering academic careers, particularly emphasizing the need for personalized, continuous development strategies and the critical role of managerial guidance. Its adoption and adaptation by other universities highlight the potential for collaborative improvement in academic career development across European University Alliances.

A workshop was held by UHD for UW, covering a range of topics. These included HeiTRACKS career support for postdoctoral researchers, strategies for effective communication and marketing to diverse and busy audiences, the development of guidelines for career development dialogues between principal investigators and postdocs, and a toolbox to support the recruitment process during appointment procedures.

4. Gender-Related Equality Standards

In the initiative led by UW (University of Warsaw) and UMIL (University of Milan), the development of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) was aimed at providing a measurable framework to assess gender equality within the academic sphere. The ambition behind this initiative was to establish a set of both quantitative and qualitative metrics that could accurately reflect the state of gender equality across various dimensions in academia.

These KPIs were envisioned to cover a range of factors:

- Gender Distribution: Measuring the proportion of male and female researchers at different career stages.
- Impact of Career Breaks: Assessing the career implications of events like maternity or paternity leave.
- Leadership Roles: Analysing the gender distribution in leadership positions.
- Research Funding: Investigating any disparities in the allocation of research funds between male and female researchers.

However, the initiative faced a significant hurdle due to the lack of comprehensive, standardized data across the participating institutions. This gap in data posed a challenge in creating a universally applicable and accurate set of KPIs. Recognizing this challenge, future efforts are now being directed towards the collection of relevant data. This process involves not only gathering existing data but also developing new methodologies for data collection that can capture the nuances of gender-related issues not only in academia, but also in academia, as well as the agreement on a common set of legal and statistical definitions of relevant concepts and issues within the country. (e.g., career paths, maternity leave, health insurance etc.).

During the workshops led by the UW and UMIL, universities also had an opportunity to present examples of actions which were the most effective and which brought the biggest change to their organizations in terms of implementing gender equality policy.

In this regard UW shared with all the partners development of the whole equality institutional framework. At the UW there is several institutions dedicated to dealing with unequal treatment, discrimination, harassment, and conflicts. It is a fully established institutional framework where those in need can seek support:

- Equality division in central administration
- Academic Ombudsman
- Rector's Committee for Prevention of Discrimination
- Anti-Mobbing Committee
- Centre for Dispute and Conflict Resolution
- Law Clinic
- The Psychological Counselling Centre
- Office for Persons with Disabilities
- Equality representatives in the organizational units

5. Work-life balance approaches

Work-life balance is a critical aspect of the human capital management strategy in academia, and WP2 has been actively monitoring and developing approaches to enhance this balance. Through data collection and workshops, WP2 has identified several key areas of focus:

Financial Support

The approaches to financial support for work-life balance measures vary significantly across universities, reflecting the diverse welfare state models in different countries. For instance, UMIL offers substantial financial support for nursery schools, addressing a crucial need in a context where such schools are not included in the public state education system. In contrast, the University of Copenhagen does not provide direct financial support for nursery schools, as they are publicly funded in Denmark. This disparity highlights the importance of tailoring financial support measures to the specific needs and contexts of each university's locale.

Psychological Support

Recognizing the importance of mental health in achieving work-life balance, all Alliance universities provide psychological consultancy services. There is a notable trend towards increasing the availability of counselling for work-related and private issues, emphasizing the overall wellbeing and mental soundness of staff and faculty.

Training and Workshops

Most 4EU+ universities have implemented courses and workshops focusing on work-life balance, with some offering specific training for researchers. A key recommendation is to expand the understanding and application of work-life balance policies beyond the human resources (HR) domain, integrating these principles as a crosscutting competence throughout the organization.

Information and Promotion

To raise awareness and encourage adoption of work-life balance measures, universities are organizing specific campaigns and initiatives. It is advised that these policies and measures be communicated effectively right from the recruitment phase, particularly during onboarding, through resources like handbooks or toolkits.

Research

To learn about the specific needs of those who have caring obligations (e.g., experience of barriers and difficulties in combining academic work and family life, organizational culture and atmosphere around parenting at the university). It is highly recommended to examine the situation and effectiveness of the work-life balance in academia.

Ongoing Collaborations and Initiatives

UMIL and UW are actively involved in hosting job-shadowing stays focused on gender policy and work-life balance, contributing to the broader dialogue and exchange of best practices within the alliance. Staff exchanges between universities (CU-UMIL, UW-UMIL, CU-UW) have been instrumental in sharing expertise and experiences, particularly around gender aspects, welcoming researchers, and best practices related to HR Award on-site visits.

Overall, these efforts by WP2 (mainly UMIL and UW who contributed massively) indicate a comprehensive and multifaceted approach to enhancing work-life balance in academia. By addressing financial and psychological needs, providing targeted training, effectively communicating policies, and fostering collaborations, the Alliance is poised to create a more supportive and equitable academic environment.

6. Future Perspectives: obstacles, challenges and what we have learnt so far

The implementation of HR policies within European University Alliances, especially in the context of attracting and retaining talents, performance and development reviews, gender-related equality standards, and work-life balance approaches, presents various challenges and obstacles:

Crisis Response

The example of supporting Ukrainian researchers and students shows the need for flexible and responsive HR policies. Adapting to crises like the Ukraine conflict requires quick action and often necessitates the development of new policies, such as financial aid and psychological support programs, which can be complex to implement uniformly across diverse institutions.

Career Development Programs

The implementation of the Performance and Development Review scheme, like at UCPH, focuses on personalized guidance for career progression. This requires not only the development of comprehensive programs but also the training of managers/senior academics and the adaptation of these programs to different institutional contexts. However, the implementation of this solution in

other universities must consider the different arrangements for the organisation of research teams, which are sometimes transitional. For this reason, team leaders were replaced by mentors during the pilot conducted by UW.

Gender Equality Initiatives

Developing Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for gender equality, as led by UW and UMIL, is complicated by the lack of comprehensive data and differing cultural and legal environments in various countries. Collaborative efforts to standardize gender equality measures across different university systems can face significant data and regulatory challenges, which could eventually be addressed by some form of policy or legal harmonization initiatives beyond the Gender Equality Plan.

Work-life Balance Policies

Monitoring work-life balance approaches, as seen in WP2, involves addressing diverse needs and cultural contexts. For instance, the financial support for nursery schools at UMIL versus UCPH reflects different welfare state models. Standardizing such policies across universities in different countries is challenging.

Cross-Institutional Collaboration and Staff Exchanges

Initiatives like staff exchanges and joint projects on gender policy require coordination across different administrative systems and legal frameworks. This includes managing logistical aspects, ensuring mutual recognition of qualifications and experiences, and aligning objectives.

Communication and Promotion

Effectively communicating policies and measures, such as through handbooks or toolkits during the onboarding phase, is crucial but can be complicated by language barriers, cultural differences, and the need for tailored approaches for different groups within the academic community.

Funding Constraints

Despite the commitment to various initiatives, funding challenges can limit the scope and effectiveness of these policies. Sustaining long-term initiatives and pilot actions requires secure and adequate funding, which is currently a significant hurdle.

Overall, while these alliances offer a rich platform for sharing best practices and fostering collaborative initiatives, they also face substantial challenges in harmonizing diverse systems, addressing legal differences, and securing the necessary resources for effective implementation.